

MANUFACTURING OF A MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE PART FOR USE IN AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: *Multifunctional, carbon fibre, battery*

1 Introduction

Lightweight engineering materials are needed to realise greener, safer and more competitive products in the automotive industry.

The need for electrical vehicles is driven by the forecasted shortage of oil based energy carriers together with the necessity to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

Efficient hybridisation/electrification requires lighter vehicle platforms than present today. One solution to this would be to introduce composites in structural parts of the car.

A step further is to integrate several functions in each component making them multifunctional. Taking it another step further into novel territory there is the idea of making multifunctional materials for use in multifunctional components as investigated by Baechle et al. [1], O'Brien et al. [2], Wetzel et al. [3], Yurchak et al. [4] and Carlson et al. [5-9].

The multifunctional component approach has been investigated by Thomas and Quidwai [10] integrating lithium thin film batteries in RC aircraft wings.

It is in this spirit the work presented here has been performed, combining structural integrity of the carbon fibre composite and electrical energy storage from lithium ion battery cells.

The multifunctional component developed was a plenum cover for a Volvo S80 car, see Figure 1, with start/stop functionality, i.e. the car automatically shuts off the combustion engine when the car is stationary and automatically turns it on

again when the car should move. The multifunctional component adds torsion stiffness to the car while replacing the extra battery needed for the start/stop function, combined with a lower weight than the components it replaces.

The plenum cover is one of several demonstrators made in the EU FP7 project StorAge, Composite Structural Power Storage for Hybrid Vehicles, where multifunctional materials such as structural capacitors, super-capacitors and batteries are being developed.

The multifunctional batteries are not yet able to compete with of the shelf Li-Ion batteries available therefore the plenum cover was made with of the shelf battery cells to demonstrate how a multifunctional component will be integrated and function within a car.

2 Materials

The composite materials used were MTM57 (epoxy) based prepregs. The pre-pregs chosen were: 2x2 Twill HS (3K) 0°/90°, MTM57/CF3200-42% RW, and UD MTM57/T700S (12k)-200-40% RW, both supplied by Cytec, UK. The twill weave was chosen for the outer skin parts of the plenum cover and the UD was chosen for the beam parts providing the needed stiffness in the transverse direction of the plenum cover.

The beam core was made from Evonic Industries Rohacell foam kindly supplied by Volvo Car Corporation, Sweden.

Batteries were kindly supplied by ETC battery and fuel cells Sweden AB. The type used where four in

series connected EIG LiFePO₄ 3.3V, 7Ah lithium ion cells giving a total of 13,2V and 7Ah.

The battery pack was internally connected by screw joints and sheets of brass insulated by heavy duty electrical tape to avoid short circuiting to the carbon fibre skins.

The external connectors were made from L-shaped aluminium pieces connected to the battery pack. The connectors were insulated by heavy duty electrical tape.

The battery pack was encased at room temperature curing epoxy and glass fibre weave, kindly supplied by Volvo Car Corporation, to provide extra electrical insulation and to increase handle ability of the battery pack when laminating the final part lamination.

The mould was manufactured from Modulan 652 tooling board and painted with car lacquer to achieve a gloss finish. Both foam and lacquer were kindly supplied by Volvo Car Corporation, Sweden.

3 Part design

The component chosen for replacement by a multifunctional composite was the plenum cover, see Figure 2 for a typical plenum cover. The plenum cover is located just in front of the windscreen mostly covered by the hood of the car. This component is large enough to contain the batteries needed and placed conveniently to add a structural functionality.

The plenum cover itself is not a structural part, merely functioning as a cover for the batteries and electronics found underneath. Therefore, to incorporate a structural function to the component, it was combined with a rally bar to provide increased torsion stiffness to the car.

The goal of the component was to replace the standard plenum cover, start/stop battery and provide an additional feature of a rally bar stiffener.

The production part today is made from injection moulded plastic with varying thickness over the part. The plenum cover is a fairly large and flat part and

was chosen because of this. The large flat part made it possible to fit the lithium-ion battery cells within this area to provide a multifunctional component.

The structural part of the plenum cover comes from the rally bar function. A rally bar is a stiffening rod, typically made from aluminium, connected to the front spring towers to provide torsional stiffness to the car, improving the cars handling on the road. A typical rally bar is depicted in Figure 3.

The chosen design was to make the outer skins of the plenum cover from a CF weave and the internal rally bar part from a UD fibre covered foam core. Here the weave skins will provide an appealing visual appearance and the UD fibres in the beam part will provide most of the mechanical performance.

Battery placement was based upon geometrical constraints, stemming from the use of an existing part. This is not ideal but to demonstrate the concept it is necessary to manufacture a component that can be interchanged in the present car available. A schematic drawing of the battery placement and electrical connection is shown in Figures 4 and 5. The batteries were connected in series to achieve total voltage of 13.2V (3.3V per battery) which is well suited for use in a cars existing electrical system.

The part design was done in Dassault Systèmes Catia V5 based on the geometry on the production part plenum cover. This made it possible to get a 3D model that was used for the structural evaluation and used to design the mould which was also done in Catia V5.

The part designed was structurally evaluated in Ansys to ensure structural integrity for the load cases supplied by Volvo Car Corporation.

A finite element simulation of the plenum cover was performed in order to ensure that the final component would withstand the loads it will be subjected to simultaneously as it protects the lithium ion battery cells from excess strain. The pictures of the meshed plenum cover skins and beam are shown in Figures 6 and 7. A cross section of the plenum cover showing the placement of the rally bar is shown in Figure 8.

The models were prepared using SpaceClaim from the original Catia CAD model. The mesh was kept as uniform as possible but due to the complex geometries some areas show a lower mesh quality. This prevents accurate estimation of local stresses to assess e.g. material failure, but was considered sufficient for the purpose of the analysis.

The rally bar was meshed using tetrahedral elements using a modified formulation to prevent volume and shear locking. These elements perform as good as hexahedral elements in the present analysis. The analysis was run using an arc length method (Riks) with an implicit solver so that the full nonlinear behaviour and potential instability could be captured.

Due to confidentiality from Volvo's part the results from the calculation cannot be revealed. The plenum cover does however comply with the Volvo requirements. This is achieved with single ply skins, one ply on each side of the batteries, and a four layer thickness of UD pre-preg surrounding the foam core beam. The thickness at the spring tower connections was set to 4 mm to ensure enough material to safely clamp the plenum cover to the car.

4 Mould design

The mould design was based on the 3D geometry made for the part. The mould was designed to be a single sided mould used with a flexible bag to achieve the pressure needed to consolidate the part.

The mould was compensated for the thermal expansion that would occur during the heating of the component. This was necessary to achieve good tolerances of the final part since the carbon fibre/epoxy composite has a very different thermal expansion than the Modulan 652 tooling board used for the mould.

5 Mould manufacture

When the mould design was completed the mould was milled from a block of Modulan 652. The surface was sanded smooth and the tooling surface was painted with high gloss car lacquer. The mould was buffed, sealed with Zywx Sealer GP and

coated with Zywx Flex-Z release agent, both supplied By B. Roos Teknik AB, Sweden.

6 Part manufacture

The part was manufactured at the concept workshop at Volvo through hand lay-up of prepregs, see Figure 9, ensuring that the battery pack was insulated from the carbon fibres in the prepregs to avoid short circuiting.

The plenum cover was made in three versions. The first version was a non functional mock up to validate the heat compensation of the mould and the plenum cover geometry in a physical car. The second and third versions were based on the lessons learned on the previous versions. The geometry around the spring tower connections was altered somewhat to produce less differences in height between the different surfaces and hence less complicated geometry to drape.

The battery pack for the final plenum cover was encased in glass fibre/epoxy to make it easier to handle and place in the final part. The plenum cover mould was used for this as well to get the correct shape of the battery pack. The lamination and final battery pack are depicted in Figures 10 and 11.

The final part was laid with debulking of every second layer. The geometry required strips of pre-preg to be used at the sharpest radii to prevent resin rich pockets and unattractive surface defects at these locations.

When lamination and debulking was completed the laminate was covered with release film, breather and bagged before connecting the vacuum and placing the mould in the oven.

The oven was ramped up to 80°C at a rate of 2°C/min and the laminate was cured at 80°C for 12 hours. MTM57 is a 120°C curing system but 80°C was chosen to avoid significant degradation of the lithium Ion batteries. After 12 hours the oven was ramped down to room temperature at a rate of 3°C/min.

After curing the laminate was demoulded and the edges were trimmed to the final shape. The final

plenum cover before trimming is depicted in Figure 12.

7 Assembly in the car

The trimmed part was used to directly replace the present plenum cover and the start stop battery without any major adjustments to the car.

The installations was easily performed by removing the standard plenum cover, battery and spring tower nuts and then connecting the new multifunctional plenum cover to the battery cables, plenum cover connectors shown in Figure 13, and tighten all nuts back up. The mounted plenum cover is depicted in Figure 14.

The car was successfully run with the multifunctional component installed and the start/stop function worked as intended.

8 Results and discussions

A multifunctional component has successfully been designed, manufactured and tested in a real life situation.

The manufacturing process may not be the best suited for mass production due to the labour intensive nature of hand lay-up of pre-pregs but the manufacture of this component has showed the potential of using composites to manufacture multifunctional parts efficiently reducing weight and space needed in automotive applications. A viable production method could be automated RTM using industrial robots to pick and place reinforcements, battery packs etc.

The weight reduction for the multifunctional component compared to the stock plenum cover, battery and an aluminium rally bar was calculated. The results are presented in Table 1. As seen in the table the weight reduction of the new system is 64% which is a significant amount of weight reduction.

9 Conclusions

A multifunctional composite automotive component has successfully been designed, manufactured and assembled in a production car. The multifunctional component combines structural functions along with

electrical energy storage and the reduction in weight compared to current solution is 64%. The component successfully shows the potential for using multifunctional components to save weight and space in future electric and hybrid vehicles.

10 Acknowledgements

Sigvard Svensson and Anders Roth at Volvo Car Corporation concept workshop are much appreciated for their assistance in the manufacture of the component.

Stefan Rösen at Volvo Car Corporation is gratefully acknowledged for his work with modelling the plenum cover in Catia V5.

Renaud Gutkin at Swerea Sicomp is gratefully acknowledged for his work with evaluating the plenum cover in Ansys.

Emil Hedlund at Swerea Sicomp is gratefully acknowledged for his assistance in manufacturing the plenum cover at Volvo Car Corporation.

Financial support from the European commission via the FP7 project grant no. 234236, StorAge is gratefully acknowledged

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Tables

Table 1. Weight comparison between current components and the multifunctional component

Component	Component weight [kg]	System weight [kg]
Plenum cover (original)	2.1	6.9
Rally bar	0.6	
Battery	4.2	
Plenum cover (multifunctional)	2.5	2.5
Weight reduction [%]		64

Figures

Fig 1. Volvo S80 (picture taken from www.volvocars.se)

Fig. 2. A typical plenum cover

Fig 3. A typical rally bar

Fig. 4. Battery placement in the multifunctional plenum cover

Fig. 5. Plenum cover internal battery connections.

Fig 6. Plenum cover skin mesh.

Fig 7. Plenum cover beam mesh.

Fig. 8 Plenum cover cross section at rally bar section.

Fig. 9 Hand lay-up of the plenum cover.

Fig. 10. Battery pack lamination.

Fig. 11. Final battery pack.

Fig. 12. Final plenum cover before edge trimming.

Fig. 13. Battery connections on final plenum cover

Fig. 14. Plenum cover mounted in a Volvo S80